

Rogue wave solutions of integrable systems

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Abstract

In this article, we review the construction of rogue wave solutions to the nonlinear Schrödinger (NLS) equation by using the Kadomtsev–Petviashvili hierarchy reduction method and Hirota’s bilinear method. These solutions are then related to the Yablonskii–Vorob’ev (YV) polynomial hierarchy and the Adler–Moser (AM) polynomial. Further on, a new Adler–Moser (NAM) polynomial is proposed, which can be related to rogue wave solutions of the Manakov system.

1 Introduction

An integrable system is a dynamical system with a sufficient number of conserved quantities.

The discovery of ‘solitons’ is derived from the report by John Scott Russell in 1834. The first report of the soliton by Russell, D. J. Korteweg, and G. de Vries derived the equation

$$u_t + 6uu_x + u_{xxx} = 0, \quad (1)$$

R. Y. Chiao, E. Garmire, and C. H. Townes wrote the nonlinear Schrödinger equation (2) in their study of optical beams, which is a simplified 1+1-dimensional form of the Ginzburg–Landau equation.

The nonlinear Schrödinger (NLS) equation is

$$iu_t = u_{xx} + 2\epsilon|u|^2u, \quad (2)$$

where $u : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, \epsilon \pm 1$. The NLS equation plays an important role in nonlinear optics and waves, as this equation appears frequently in these studies [1–3]. The nonlinearity could be focusing or defocusing, depending on the sign of the nonlinear coefficient. For the focusing case, the result would be bright solitons, and for the non-focusing case, the result would be dark solitons [4].

Figure 1: Both equations can serve as basic mathematical models of waves and water [5, 6]

Rogue waves, also called freak waves, are extremely dangerous and unpredictable surface waves. They are defined as waves whose height is more than twice the significant wave height in oceanography. According to statistics, a minimum of 22 supercarriers have been lost due to rogue waves from 1969 to 1994. The

New Year wave was recorded on the Draupner platform in the North Sea on January 1, 1995, at 15:20 [7].

In addition to the ocean, rogue waves can also be recreated in laboratories. In 2019, a team from the Universities of Oxford and Edinburgh recreated the Draupner wave, a typical example of a rogue wave, in a lab [8]. Not only that, the phenomenon of rogue waves may also be observed in air, as some named “rogue air currents” [9]. The first model of the rogue wave is the nonlinear Schrödinger equation, which models the behavior of such waves in the context of ocean waves by John N. (Jack) M. Osborne and his colleagues in the 1980s. The model provided a concrete mathematical framework to understand how rogue waves could form and evolve [10]. In addition to the NLS equation, equations such as the Korteweg-de Vries equation, Boussinesq equation, and the Davey-Stewartson equation can also be used to calculate rogue wave solutions [11–13]. The basic principle under rogue waves is how multiple wave systems converge and temporarily combine, creating a much larger wave. This is called constructive interference. Rogue waves are typically short-lived, lasting only a few minutes before dissipating; however, they may create significant destruction and losses [14]. Over the past few decades, polynomials such as the Yablonskii-Vorob’ev polynomial and the Adler-Moser polynomial have been developed to estimate rogue wave patterns.

In this paper, we first introduce the dark soliton and rogue wave solutions of the NLS equation. Then, we will discuss the two existing polynomials that are used to estimate rogue waves. Lastly, we will introduce the polynomial we built to estimate rogue waves.

2 Soliton solutions

In this section, we will introduce the bright and dark soliton solutions of the Korteweg-de Vries (KdV) equation and the nonlinear Schrödinger (NLS) equation.

Theorem 2.1. [15] The Korteweg-de Vries equation (1) admits the bright soliton solution

$$u = 2 \log(f)_{xx}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$f = \det_{1 \leq i, j \leq n} \left(c_i \delta_{i, j} \exp(-\xi_i - \eta_j) + \frac{1}{p_i + q_j} \left(-\frac{p_i}{q_j} \right)^n \right), \quad (4)$$

and

$$\xi_i = p_i x + 4p_i^3 t + \xi_{i0}, \quad \eta_j = q_j x + 4q_j^3 t + \eta_{j0}. \quad (5)$$

Theorem 2.2. [16] The NLS equation (2) admits the dark soliton solutions

$$u(x, t) = \rho \frac{g(x, t)}{f(x, t)} e^{i(cx - \omega t)}, \quad (6)$$

where $c, \rho, \epsilon \in \mathbb{R}$, $\omega = 2\rho^2\epsilon - c^2$,

$$g(x, t) = \tau_1(x, t), \quad f(x, t) = \tau_0(x, t), \quad (7)$$

and $\tau_k(x, t)$ is defined as

$$\tau_k(x, t) = \det_{1 \leq i, j \leq N} \left(c_i \delta_{ij} + \frac{1}{p_i + q_j} \left(-\frac{p_i - ic}{q_j + ic} \right)^k e^{\xi_i + \xi_j^*} \right), \quad (8)$$

with

$$\xi_i = p_i x - p_i^2 i t + \xi_{i,0}. \quad (9)$$

Here, δ_{ij} refers to the Kronecker delta, N is a positive integer, $p_i = q_i^*$ and p_i, q_i satisfy the following equation

$$(p_i - ic)(q_i + ic) = -\epsilon\rho^2, \quad (10)$$

where ‘*’ denotes complex conjugation.

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2.1 Dynamics of bright soliton solutions of the KdV equation

For all bright soliton solutions, there will always be at least one collision, except for the 1-soliton solution. Since the shape for the solitons would maintain their speed and shape after the collisions, these collisions are therefore elastic.

Figure 2: 1-bright soliton solution of Korteweg-de Vries equation (1) with parameters $p_1 = 1 + i, q_1 = 1 - i, c = 1, \rho = 1$.

Figure 3: 2-bright soliton solution of Korteweg-de Vries equation (1) with parameters $p_1 = 1 + i, q_1 = 1 - i, c = 1, \rho = 1, p_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{1}{2}, q_2 = \frac{\sqrt{i}}{2} - \frac{i}{2}, c = 1, \rho = 1$.

Figure 4: 3-bright soliton solution of Korteweg-de Vries equation (1) with parameters $p_1 = 1 + i, q_1 = 1 - i, c = 1, \rho = 1, p_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{1}{2}, q_2 = \frac{\sqrt{i}}{2} - \frac{i}{2}, c = 1, \rho = 1, p_3 = \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} + \frac{i}{4}, q_3 = \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} - \frac{i}{4}, c = 1, \rho = 1$.

2.2 Dynamics of dark soliton solutions of the NLS equation

For all dark soliton solutions, there will always be at least one collision, except for the 1-soliton solution. Since the shape for the solitons remains the same after the collisions, we can infer these collisions are therefore elastic.

Figure 5: 1-dark soliton solution of nonlinear Schrödinger equation (2) with parameters $p_1 = 1 + i, q_1 = 1 - i, c = 1, \rho = 1$.

Figure 6: 2-dark soliton solution of nonlinear Schrödinger equation (2) with parameters $p_1 = 1 + i, q_1 = 1 - i, c = 1, \rho = 1, p_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{1}{2}, q_2 = \frac{\sqrt{i}}{2} - \frac{i}{2}, c = 1, \rho = 1$.

Figure 7: 3-dark soliton solution of nonlinear Schrödinger equation (2) with parameters $p_1 = 1 + i, q_1 = 1 - i, c = 1, \rho = 1, p_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{1}{2}, q_2 = \frac{\sqrt{i}}{2} - \frac{i}{2}, c = 1, \rho = 1, p_3 = \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} + \frac{i}{4}, q_3 = \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} - \frac{i}{4}, c = 1, \rho = 1$.

3 Rogue wave solutions

This section uses the NLS equation and the Schur polynomials to derive the first, second, and third rogue wave solutions. Then, the patterns of solutions in different orders are identified.

The Schur polynomials $S_k(\mathbf{x})$, with $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots)$, are defined by

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} S_k(\mathbf{x})\epsilon^k = \exp\left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} x_k \epsilon^k\right). \tag{11}$$

To be more specific, we have

$$S_0(\mathbf{x}) = 1, \quad S_1(\mathbf{x}) = x_1, \quad S_2(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2}x_1^2 + x_2, \quad \dots, \quad S_j(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{l_1+2l_2+\dots+ml_m=j} \left(\prod_{i=1}^m \frac{x_i^{l_i}}{l_i!}\right). \tag{12}$$

Further, we define $S_j(\mathbf{x}) \equiv 0$ for $j < 0$.

Theorem 3.1. [17] The NLS equation (2) with $\epsilon = 1$ admits the rogue wave solutions

$$u(x, t) = \frac{g(x, t)}{f(x, t)} e^{-2it}, \tag{13}$$

where

$$g(x, t) = \tau_1(x, t), \quad f(x, t) = \tau_0(x, t), \tag{14}$$

and $\tau_k(x, t)$ is defined as

$$\tau_k(x, t) = \det_{1 \leq i, j \leq N} \left(m_{2i-1, 2j-1}^{(k)} \right), \tag{15}$$

with

$$m_{i,j}^{(k)} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{\min(i,j)} \frac{1}{4^\nu} S_{i-\nu}(\mathbf{x}^+(n) + \nu \mathbf{s}) S_{j-\nu}(\mathbf{x}^-(n) + \nu \mathbf{s}), \tag{16}$$

Here, N is a positive integer, vectors $\mathbf{x}^\pm(n) = (x_1^\pm, x_2^\pm, \dots)$ are defined by

$$x_1^\pm = x \mp 2it \pm n, \quad x_{2k}^\pm = 0, \quad x_{2k+1}^+ = \frac{x - 2^{2k+1}(it)}{(2k+1)!} + a_{2k+1}, \quad x_{2k+1}^- = \frac{x + 2^{2k+1}(it)}{(2k+1)!} + a_{2k+1}^*,$$

with $k \geq 1$ and the asterisk $*$ representing complex conjugation, and $\mathbf{s} = (0, s_2, 0, s_4, \dots)$ are coefficients from the expansion

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} s_j \lambda^j = \ln \left[\frac{2}{\lambda} \tanh \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} \right) \right]. \tag{17}$$

3.1 Dynamics of rogue wave solutions of the NLS equation

Table 1: Parameters of the figures.

Figures	Parameters
Fig. 8	$p_1 = -1 + i, q_1 = -1 - i, c = 1, \rho = 1$
Fig. 10	$p_2 = \sqrt{3}/2 + 1/2i, q_2 = \sqrt{3}/2 - 1/2i, c = 1, \rho = 1$
Fig. 14	$p_3 = \sqrt{7}/4 + 1/4i, q_3 = \sqrt{7}/4 - 1/4i, c = 1, \rho = 1$

3.1.1 First-order rogue wave solutions

To obtain the first-order rogue wave solution, we can take $N = 1$ in Theorem 3.1. The first-order rogue wave solution admits the following expression:

$$u = \frac{e^{-2it} (16t^2 + 16it + 4x^2 - 3)}{16t^2 + 4x^2 + 1}.$$

Figure 8: First-order rogue wave solution of NLS equation (2).

The maximum and minimum of the first-order rougewave can be found by calculating the solution of the equations $u_t = 0$ and $u_x = 0$, which results in three roots (x, t) .

For three roots $(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, 0), (-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, 0), (0, 0)$, by plugging into the equation $(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, 0)$ and $(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, 0)$ result in 0 and $(0, 0)$ results in 3.

Thus the first-order rougewave reaches a local minimum of 0 at $(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, 0)$ and $(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, 0)$ and reaches a local maximum of 3 at $(0, 0)$.

3.1.2 Second-order rogue wave solutions

To obtain the first-order rogue wave solution, we can take $N = 2$ in Theorem 3.1. Second order rougewave while $a_3 = 0$:

$$u = e^{-2it} \frac{G}{F},$$

$$G = 4(12(4t + i)(4t + 3i)x^4 + 3(-15 + 32t(t(-15 + 8t(t + 2i)) - 3i))x^2 + 115200t(t + i)x + 4t(t(-117 + 16t(t(-33 + 16t(t + 3i)) + 6i)) - 45i) + 16x^6 - 9600x^3) - 86400x + 5760045,$$

$$F = 4096t^6 + 768t^4(4x^2 + 9) + 48t^2(8x(2x^3 - 3x + 1200) + 33) + 4x(x(4x(4x^3 + 3x - 2400) + 27) + 7200) + 5760009.$$

Second order rougewave while $a_3 = 50$:

$$u = e^{-2it} \frac{G}{F},$$

$$G = 4(12(4t + i)(4t + 3i)x^4 + 3(2385 + 32t(t(-15 + 8t(t + 2i)) - 153i))x^2 + 28800t(t + i)x + 4t(t(-7317 + 16t(t(-33 + 16t(t + 3i)) + 306i)) - 945i) + 16x^6 - 2400x^3) - 21600x + 7245,$$

$$F = 4096t^6 + 768t^4(4x^2 + 9) + 76800it^3 + 48t^2(8x(2x^3 - 3x + 300) + 33) - 14400it(4x^2 - 3) + 4x(x(4x(4x^3 + 3x - 600) + 27) + 1800) + 9.$$

Figure 9: Second-order rogue wave solution of NLS equation (2) with parameters $a_3 = 0$.

Figure 10: Second-order rogue wave solution of NLS equation (2) with parameters $a_3 = 50$.

Through comparison between the two figures, the change of a_3 will affect the position of three rougewaves, as when a_3 equals 0 the three waves are gathered together whereas when a_3 equals 50 they're separated apart.

3.1.3 Third-order rogue wave solutions

To obtain the first-order rogue wave solution, we can take $N = 3$ in Theorem 3.1.

$$m = \begin{vmatrix} m_{11} & m_{13} & m_{15} \\ m_{31} & m_{33} & m_{35} \\ m_{51} & m_{53} & m_{55} \end{vmatrix}, \tag{18}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 m_{11} &= S_1(x^+(n))S_1(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_0(x^+(n) + \rho)S_0(x^-(n) + \rho), \\
 m_{13} &= S_1(x^+(n))S_3(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_0(x^+(n) + \rho)S_2(x^-(n) + \rho), \\
 m_{15} &= S_1(x^+(n))S_5(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_0(x^+(n) + \rho)S_4(x^-(n) + \rho), \\
 m_{31} &= S_3(x^+(n))S_1(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_2(x^+(n) + \rho)S_0(x^-(n) + \rho), \\
 m_{33} &= S_3(x^+(n))S_3(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_2(x^+(n) + \rho)S_2(x^-(n) + \rho) + \frac{1}{16}S_1(x^+(n) + 2\rho)S_1(x^-(n) + 2\rho) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{64}S_0(x^+(n) + 3\rho)S_0(x^-(n) + 3\rho), \\
 m_{35} &= S_3(x^+(n))S_5(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_2(x^+(n) + \rho)S_4(x^-(n) + \rho) + \frac{1}{16}S_1(x^+(n) + 2\rho)S_3(x^-(n) + 2\rho) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{64}S_0(x^+(n) + 3\rho)S_2(x^-(n) + 3\rho), \\
 m_{51} &= S_5(x^+(n))S_1(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_4(x^+(n) + \rho)S_0(x^-(n) + \rho), \\
 m_{53} &= S_5(x^+(n))S_3(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_4(x^+(n) + \rho)S_2(x^-(n) + \rho) + \frac{1}{16}S_3(x^+(n) + 2\rho)S_1(x^-(n) + 2\rho) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{64}S_2(x^+(n) + 3\rho)S_0(x^-(n) + 3\rho), \\
 m_{55} &= S_5(x^+(n))S_5(x^-(n)) + \frac{1}{4}S_4(x^+(n) + \rho)S_4(x^-(n) + \rho) + \frac{1}{16}S_3(x^+(n) + 2\rho)S_3(x^-(n) + 2\rho), \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{64}S_2(x^+(n) + 3\rho)S_2(x^-(n) + 3\rho) + \frac{1}{256}S_1(x^+(n) + 3\rho)S_1(x^-(n) + 3\rho) + \\
 &\quad \frac{1}{1024}S_0(x^+(n) + 3\rho)S_0(x^-(n) + 3\rho),
 \end{aligned}$$

Expanding the equation we get:

$$m_{11} = (x - 2it + n)(x + 2it - n) + \frac{1}{4}. \tag{19}$$

Figure 11: Third-order rogue wave solution of NLS equation (2) with parameters $a_3 = 0, a_5 = 0$.

Figure 12: Third-order Rogue wave solution of NLS equation (2) with parameters $a_3 = 0, a_5 = 50$.

Figure 13: Third-order rogue wave solution of NLS equation (2) with parameters $a_3 = 50, a_5 = 0$.

Figure 14: Third-order rogue wave solution of NLS equation (2) with parameters $a_3 = 50, a_5 = 50$.

Parameters a_3 and a_5 determine whether the waves would gather together or spread out. When their absolute values are greater, the waves will spread out, and vice versa. Through comparison, changing a_3 will result in the waves spreading in a triangular shape, and changing a_5 will result in the waves spreading in a pentagonal shape.

Remark 1. Through observations of graphs of different order rogue waves, a pattern appears as while the first-order rogue wave has one solution, the second-order rogue wave has three, and the third-order rogue wave has six. It could be deduced that the n -th order rogue wave has $1+2+3+\dots+n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ solutions.

4 Rogue wave patterns in the NLS equation

In this section, we will obtain the roots of the Yablonskii–Vorob’ev polynomial hierarchy (YV polynomial hierarchy) and the Adler Moser polynomial (AM polynomial). We will then compare the roots with the real and predicted rogue wave solutions and identify patterns associated with them.

4.1 Preliminaries

To study the rogue wave patterns, we first introduce two polynomial hierarchies.

4.1.1 Yablonskii–Vorob’ev polynomial hierarchy

To define the Yablonskii–Vorob’ev polynomial hierarchy, let $P_k^{[m]}(z)$ be the generalized Schur polynomial defined by [18]:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_k^{[m]} e^k = \exp\left(z\epsilon - \frac{2^{2m}}{2m+1} \epsilon^{2m+1}\right), \quad (20)$$

where m is a positive integer.

Then, the Yablonskii–Vorob’ev hierarchy $Q_N^{[m]}(Z)$ is given by the $N * N$ determinant:

$$Q_N^{[m]}(Z) = C_N \begin{vmatrix} p_1^{[m]}(z) & p_0^{[m]}(z) & \dots & p_{2-N}^{[m]}(z) \\ p_3^{[m]}(z) & p_2^{[m]}(z) & \dots & p_{4-N}^{[m]}(z) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ p_{2N-1}^{[m]}(z) & p_{2N-2}^{[m]}(z) & \dots & p_N^{[m]}(z) \end{vmatrix}, \quad (21)$$

where $p_k^{[m]}(z) = 0$ if $k < 0$ and C_N ensures that the coefficient of the highest order of z equals 1.

4.1.2 Roots of Yablonskii–Vorob’ev polynomial hierarchy

The equation of Yablonskii–Vorob’ev hierarchy when $N = 1$ gives:

$$Q_1^{[m]}(z) = C_1 \left| p_1^{[m]}(z) \right|. \quad (22)$$

By plugging into equation (17), when $m = 1$,

$$Q_1^{[1]} = C_1 \times z \quad (23)$$

, where $C_1 = 1$ so that the coefficient of highest order of z equals 1.

To get the root of $Q_1^{[1]}$ we set it equal to 0 and solve the equation, giving the solution of $z = 0 + 0i$. Through calculation and expansion of the equation, $Q_1^{[m]}(z)$ is always equal to 1 regarding the value of m .

The equation of Yablonskii–Vorob’ev hierarchy when $N = 2$ gives:

$$Q_2^{[m]}(z) = C_N \begin{vmatrix} p_1^{[m]}(z) & p_0^{[m]}(z) \\ p_3^{[m]}(z) & p_2^{[m]}(z) \end{vmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

By plugging into equation (17), when $m = 1$,

$$Q_2^{[1]} = C_2 \left| \begin{matrix} z & 1 \\ \frac{1}{6}(z^3 - 8) & \frac{z^2}{2} \end{matrix} \right| = \frac{C_2}{3} (z^3 + 4). \quad (25)$$

Following the rule that C_N must ensure the coefficient of highest order of z equal to 1, $C_2 = 3$.

Solving $z^3 + 4 = 0$, we get the roots for $Q_2^{[2]}$.

The equation of Yablonskii–Vorob’ev hierarchy when $N = 3$ gives:

$$Q_3^{[m]}(z) = C_3 \begin{vmatrix} p_1^{[m]}(z) & p_0^{[m]}(z) & p_{-1}^{[m]}(z) \\ p_3^{[m]}(z) & p_2^{[m]}(z) & p_1^{[m]}(z) \\ p_5^{[m]}(z) & p_4^{[m]}(z) & p_3^{[m]}(z) \end{vmatrix}. \tag{26}$$

By plugging into equation (17), when $m = 1$,

$$Q_3^{[1]} = C_3 \begin{vmatrix} z & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{6}(z^3 - 8) & \frac{z^2}{2} & z \\ \frac{1}{120}(z^5 - 80z^2) & \frac{1}{24}(z^4 - 32z) & \frac{1}{6}(z^3 - 8) \end{vmatrix} = \frac{C_3}{45}(z^6 + 20z^3 - 80), \tag{27}$$

$C_3 = 45$. Solving $(z^6 + 20z^3 - 80) = 0$, we get the roots for $Q_3^{[1]}(z)$.

When $m = 2$,

$$Q_3^{[2]} = C_3 \begin{vmatrix} z & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{z^3}{6}(z^3 - 8) & \frac{z^2}{2} & z \\ \frac{1}{120}(z^5 - 384) & \frac{z^4}{24} & \frac{z^3}{6} \end{vmatrix} = \frac{C_3}{45} \times z(z^5 - 144), \tag{28}$$

$C_3 = 45$. Solving $z(z^5 - 144) = 0$, we get the roots for $Q_3^{[2]}(z)$.

Through observation, when m is equal or greater to N , the root will always be 0. C_N stays constant as long as N is not changed, no matter the value of m . The change of m will change the shape of the solution graph. When N increases, the number of solutions increases as well, and the total number of solutions = $2N - 1$.

4.1.3 Alder-Moser Polynomial

Alder-Moser Polynomials $\theta_N(z)$ can be written as a determinant [19]

$$\theta_N(z) = c_N \times \begin{vmatrix} \theta_1(z) & \theta_0(z) & \dots & \theta_{2-N}(z) \\ \theta_3(z) & \theta_2(z) & \dots & \theta_{4-N}(z) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \theta_{2N-1}(z) & \theta_{2N-2}(z) & \dots & \theta_N(z) \end{vmatrix}. \tag{29}$$

where $\theta_k(z)$ are Schur polynomials defined by

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \theta_k(z) \epsilon^k = \text{exp}(z\epsilon + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \kappa_j \epsilon^{2j+1}), \tag{30}$$

$\theta_k(z) = 0$ if $k < 0$, $c_N = \prod_{j=1}^N (2j - 1)!!$.

4.1.4 Roots of Alder-Moser Polynomial

The equation of Alder-Moser Polynomial when $N = 1$ gives

$$\theta_1(z) = c_1 \times z, \tag{31}$$

where $c_1 = 1$ so that the coefficient of the highest order of z equal to 1. To get the root of $\theta_1(z)$ we set it equal to 0 and solve the equation, giving the solution of $z = 0 + 0i$. The value of constant κ_j does not affect the equation and roots of $\theta_1(z)$

The equation of Alder-Moser Polynomial when $N = 2$ gives

$$\theta_2(z) = c_2 \times \begin{vmatrix} z & 1 \\ \frac{1}{6}(6\kappa_1 + z^3) & \frac{z^2}{2} \end{vmatrix} = \frac{c_2}{3}(z^3 - 3\kappa_1) \tag{32}$$

Figure 15: Plot of the roots of the Yablonskii–Vorob’ev polynomial hierarchy.

where $c_2 = 3$ so that the coefficient of the highest order of z equal to 1. As long as $\kappa_1 \neq 0$, the root of $\theta_1(z)$ will be changed based on the value of κ_1 . However, the shape of the graph will not be changed.

Figure 16: Root of $\theta_2(z)$ of Alder-Moser Polynomial with parameter of $\kappa_1 = 1$

The equation of Alder-Moser Polynomial when $N = 3$ gives

$$\theta_3(z) = c_3 \times \begin{vmatrix} z & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{6}(6\kappa_1 + z^3) & \frac{z^2}{2} & z \\ \frac{1}{120}(120\kappa_2 + z^5 + 60\kappa_1 z^2) & \frac{1}{24}(z^4 + 24\kappa_1 z) & \frac{1}{6}(6\kappa_1 + z^3) \end{vmatrix} = c_3(-\kappa_1^2 + \frac{z^6}{45} - \frac{\kappa_1 z^3}{3} + \kappa_2 z), \quad (33)$$

where $c_3 = 45$ so that the coefficient of the highest order of z equal to 1.

Figure 17: Root of $\theta_3(z)$ of Alder-Moser Polynomial with parameter of a: $\{\kappa_1 = 1, \kappa_2 = 1\}$; b: $\{\kappa_1 = 1, \kappa_2 = 2\}$; c: $\{\kappa_1 = 2, \kappa_2 = 1\}$

Other examples of solutions

Figure 18: Root of $\theta_5(z)$ of Alder-Moser Polynomial with parameter of a: $\{\kappa_1 = 1, \kappa_2 = 1, \kappa_3 = 1, \kappa_4 = 1\}$; b: $\{\kappa_1 = i, \kappa_2 = i, \kappa_3 = i, \kappa_4 = i\}$; c: $\{\kappa_1 = 4, \kappa_2 = 6, \kappa_3 = 8, \kappa_4 = 10\}$

4.2 Rogue wave patterns

Theorem 4.1. [20] For the N th-order rogue wave solution $u_N(x, t)$ of the nonlinear Schrödinger equation with a sufficiently large parameter $|a_{2m+1}| \gg 1$, corresponding to Y-V polynomials, the solution exhibits distinct asymptotic behaviors in different regions:

Far away from the origin, with $\sqrt{x^2 + t^2} = O(|a_{2m+1}|^{1/(2m+1)})$, the N th order rogue wave $u_N(x, t)$ in equation (13) separates into u_p fundamental (Peregrine) rogue waves, where $N_p = \frac{1}{2}[N(N + 1) - N_0(N_0 + 1)]$. These Peregrine waves are $\hat{u}_1(x - \hat{x}_0, t - \hat{t}_0)e^{it}$, where

$$\hat{u}_1(x, t) = 1 - \frac{4(1 + 2it)}{1 + 4x^2 + 4t^2}, \tag{34}$$

and their positions (\hat{x}_0, \hat{t}_0) are given by

$$\hat{x}_0 + i\hat{t}_0 = z_0 \left(-\frac{2m + 1}{2^{2m} a_{2m+1}}\right)^{\frac{1}{2m+1}}, \tag{35}$$

with z_0 being any one of the N_p simple nonzero roots of $Q_N^{[m]}(z)$. The error of this Peregrine wave approximation is $O(|a_{2m+1}|^{-1/(2m+1)})$.

In the neighborhood of the origin, where $\sqrt{x^2 + t^2} = O(1)$, $u_N(x, t)$ is approximately a lower N_0 th order rogue wave $u_{N_0}(x, t)$ is given by equation (13) with its internal parameters $a_3, a_5, \dots, a_{2N-1}$ being the first $N_0 - 1$ values in the parameter set $(a_3, a_5, \dots, a_{2N-1})$ of the original rogue wave $u_{N_0}(x, t)$ is $O(|a_{2m+1}|^{-1})$. Expressed mathematically, when $\sqrt{x^2 + t^2} = O(1)$,

$$u_N(x, t; a_3, a_5, \dots, a_{2N-1}) = u_{N_0}(x, t; a_3, a_5, \dots, a_{2N_0-1}) + O(|a_{2m+1}|^{-1}), |a_{2m+1}| \gg 1. \tag{36}$$

If $N_0 = 0$, then there will not be such a lower-order rogue wave in the neighborhood of the origin, and $u_N(x, t)$ asymptotically approaches the constant background e^{it} there as $|a_{2m+1}| \rightarrow \infty$.

Theorem 4.2. [21] Expressed mathematically, when $[(x - \hat{x}_0)^2 + (t - \hat{t}_0)^2]^{1/2} = O(1)$, we have the following solution asymptotics

$$u_N(x, t; a_3, a_5, \dots, a_{2N_0-1}) = \hat{u}_1(x - \hat{x}_0, t - \hat{t}_0)e^{it} + O(|a_{2m+1}|^{-1/(2m+1)}), |a_{2m+1}| \gg 1. \tag{37}$$

It correspond to a AM polynomial when (x, t) is not in the neighborhood of any of these N_p Peregrine waves, or $\sqrt{x^2 + t^2}$ is larger than $O(|a_{2m+1}|^{1/(2m+1)})$, $u_N(x, t)$ symptotically approaches the constant background e^{it} as $|a_{2m+1}| \rightarrow \infty$.

4.3 Comparison between real and predict rogue wave patterns

4.3.1 Rogue wave patterns associated with YV polynomials

The two parameters that determine the number and values of the roots of the Yablonskii–Vorob’ev polynomial are N and m . As long as N stays the same, C_N is constant. The value of N determines the number of roots of the hierarchy, which is exactly $\frac{N(N+1)}{2}$. The value of m determines the value of the roots, in other words, how the roots appear on the graph. The smaller the value of m , the roots appear more like a triangle. The larger the m , the roots appear more like a circle where several roots are in the center and the other roots surround them [21]. The estimations of Adler-Moser and the Yablonskii-Vorob’ev polynomials could be applied in the real life:

Figure 19: Comparison between higher order rogue waves and roots of YV polynomial hierarchy.

4.3.2 Rogue wave patterns associated with Alder-Moser polynomials

Figure 20: The first row is roots of AM polynomials, the second prediction of rogue waves, and the third real-life rogue waves.

5 Rogue wave pattern in the Manakov system

In this section we defines a new type of polynomial called the new Adler-Moser (NAM) polynomial. We are going to compare the roots of the new Adler-Moser polynomial with rogue wave solutions of the Manakov System and try to identity any possible pattern.

5.1 Introduction

Define a new type of polynomials as

$$\mathcal{P}_N(z) = d_N \begin{vmatrix} p_1(z) & p_0(z) & \cdots & p_{2-N}(z) \\ p_4(z) & p_3(z) & \cdots & p_{5-N}(z) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ p_{3N-2}(z) & p_{3N-3}(z) & \cdots & p_{2N-1}(z) \end{vmatrix}, \tag{38}$$

where d_N is a constant, p_k are Schur polynomials defined by

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_k(z)\epsilon^k = \exp(z\epsilon + \kappa_2\epsilon^2 + \kappa_4\epsilon^4 + \kappa_5\epsilon^5 + \kappa_7\epsilon^7 + \cdots). \tag{39}$$

5.2 Roots of the new polynomial

The equation of the new polynomial when $N = 1$ gives

$$P_1(z) = d_1 * z, \tag{40}$$

where d_1 is the coefficient that ensure the highest order of z in the equation is 1. In order to get the root of $P_1(z)$, we set its value to zero and solve the equation. Through calculations, the root of $P_1(z)$ is $z = 0 + 0i$. The value of $P_1(z)$ is not related to the constant κ_j .

The equation of the new polynomial when $N = 2$ gives

$$P_2(z) = c_2 * \left| \begin{matrix} z & 1 \\ \frac{1}{6}(z^3 + 12z) & \frac{1}{2}(z^2 + 4) \end{matrix} \right| = \frac{c_2}{2} (z^2 + 2\kappa_1) \tag{41}$$

in which $c_2 = 80$ in order for the highest order of z has a coefficient of 1. The roots of $P_2(z)$ changes according to κ_1 ($\kappa_1 \neq 0$). The equation of the new polynomial when $N = 3$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} P_2(z) &= c_2 * \left| \begin{matrix} z & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{24}(z^4 + 24z^2 + 216) & \frac{1}{6}(z^3 + 12z) & \frac{1}{2}(z^2 + 4) \\ \frac{z^7 + 84z^5 + 7560z^3 + 2520z^2 + 77280z + 30240}{5040} & \frac{z^6 + 60z^4 + 3240z^2 + 720z + 11040}{720} & \frac{z^5 + 40z^3 + 1080z + 120}{120} \end{matrix} \right| \\ &= \frac{1}{80} (20z^2 (\kappa_1^2 - 2\kappa_2) + 40\kappa_1 (\kappa_1^2 + 2\kappa_2) + 10\kappa_1 z^4 - 80\kappa_3 z + z^6), \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

in which $c_2 = 80$ in order for the highest order of z has a coefficient of 1. The roots of $P_2(z)$ changes according to κ_1 ($\kappa_1 \neq 0$).

Some roots of the New Polynomial:

Figure 21: The root of $\theta_5(z)$ of the new Adler-Moser polynomial with parameters $\{\kappa_1 = 1, \kappa_2 = 1, \kappa_3 = 1, \kappa_4 = 1\}$, $\{\kappa_1 = 1, \kappa_2 = -1, \kappa_3 = 1, \kappa_4 = -1\}$, $\{\kappa_1 = 1, \kappa_2 = 4, \kappa_3 = 7, \kappa_4 = 2\}$, $\{\kappa_1 = 2, \kappa_2 = 7, \kappa_3 = 1, \kappa_4 = 4\}$, $\{\kappa_1 = i, \kappa_2 = 0, \kappa_3 = i, \kappa_4 = 0\}$, $\{\kappa_1 = i, \kappa_2 = i, \kappa_3 = i, \kappa_4 = i\}$ respectively

5.3 Rogue wave patterns associated with NAM polynomials

The NAM polynomial we created has applications in real life, as shown in the graphs below. The figures show how the rogue waves, predicted locations, and roots correspond to each other, with a non-linear transformation. By utilizing this pattern, we could predict complex rogue waves in real life.

Figure 22: The rogue wave solution of the Manakov System with parameters and its predicted locations. $P_3(z)$, $\{\kappa_1 = 1, \kappa_2 = 1, \kappa_3 = 1, \kappa_4 = 1\}$.

6 Conclusion

Rogue waves are waves appearing in the ocean that are at least twice higher than typical waves in a given sea state. They are extremely unpredictable and dangerous. Throughout history, they have created huge losses and destruction. One equation that could describe the rogue waves is the NLS equation. Two polynomials that were used to estimate rogue wave patterns were the Yablonskii-Vorob'ev polynomial and the Adler-Moser polynomial. These two polynomials could be used to estimate when will a rogue wave appear at what location.

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